

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

Doctoral Candidate Hoàng Quyên¹, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Thái Thị Kim Oanh²

^{1,2}Vinh University

ABSTRACT: This paper proposes a theoretical framework for provincial government policies supporting cooperative development. The policy approach emphasizes the creation of an enabling environment for the establishment, operation, and enhancement of the sustainable development of cooperatives. Using a specific local case in Vietnam, the study focuses on the content of cooperative development support policies implemented by the Nghe An provincial government, including: policy foundations, objectives, principles, policy actors, target groups, and three core policy components, namely: policies supporting establishment and organizational model transformation; policies supporting production and business operations; and policies supporting sustainable development. The research findings analyze and evaluate the current state of cooperative development support policies and propose key recommendations to improve and strengthen the policy framework for cooperative development in Nghe An province.

KEYWORDS: cooperative development; cooperative development support policies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The cooperative model, with its distinctive characteristics in terms of organizational structure, human resources, capital, operational activities, sectors, and geographical scope, has demonstrated a significant role in local economic, social, and environmental development—particularly in rural and agricultural areas—more so than any other form of production or business organization. According to Dogarawa (2010), cooperatives are effective instruments that enable people to control their livelihoods. They play an increasingly important role in facilitating employment creation, economic growth, and social development by achieving objectives related to enhancing organizational viability, improving services to members, and sustaining economically viable, innovative, and competitive enterprises.

Nghe An is a province in Vietnam where the development of cooperatives has made substantial contributions to employment generation and income improvement, especially in rural areas. In recent years, the Nghe An provincial government has promulgated various policies related to cooperatives in order to implement central government directives on cooperative development, such as the 2012 Law on Cooperatives and the 2023 Law on Cooperatives. Notably, these include policies and plans aimed at supporting cooperative development, particularly in the agricultural sector. The province's policies have been formulated and implemented based on national guidelines and policies on cooperative development support, while being adapted to local conditions. Since the enactment of the 2012 Law on Cooperatives, the Nghe An provincial government has introduced several innovations and effective initiatives in policies supporting cooperative development. Cooperatives have contributed significantly to production development, economic and labor restructuring, job creation, poverty reduction, infrastructure development, and the establishment of new economic models and production relations in rural areas. The contribution of cooperatives to the province's Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) has steadily increased, reaching 7.7% in 2023—an increase of 0.9 percentage points compared to 2018 (Ministry of Planning and Investment, 2023a).

However, in practice, cooperatives in Nghe An province continue to face numerous challenges. Most cooperatives suffer from capital shortages; their capacity to mobilize capital from members is limited, and access to bank credit remains difficult. Production equipment is often outdated, and production scales are small. Cooperative members have not fully demonstrated their roles and responsibilities in relation to cooperative operations and sustainability. In addition, the managerial capacity of cooperative leaders is limited, and they have not been sufficiently proactive in responding to market mechanisms. Furthermore, most cooperatives have not yet established effective value chains; their competitiveness remains weak; linkages and partnerships among cooperatives, as well as between cooperatives and other economic organizations, are modest and of limited effectiveness. There is also a lack of enterprises willing to engage in joint ventures or partnerships to secure output markets for cooperatives. As a result, cooperatives in the province have not effectively fulfilled their role as intermediaries connecting members to markets, and the direct economic

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

benefits delivered to members remain limited. These difficulties can be attributed, in part, to the fact that certain provincial policies supporting cooperative development have not been fully aligned with the current conditions and developmental context of cooperatives in Nghe An.

A number of studies have examined solutions and policies supporting cooperative development from various perspectives. Some studies have focused on developing theoretical frameworks and discussing lessons learned from policies supporting cooperative development, such as Adeler (2014) on Enabling Policy Environments for Cooperative Development: A Comparative Experience; Rowe et al. (2018) on Policy Supports for Cooperative Development: Learning from Co-op Hot Spots; and Nguyen Thi Hai Ninh (2021) on Policies Supporting Agricultural Cooperatives in Vietnam: An Experience from Agricultural Cooperatives in the Red River Delta. In the context of Nghe An province, several studies have addressed solutions for supporting cooperative development, including Nguyen Thi Hai Yen (2018) on agricultural development in Nghe An towards modernization under conditions of international economic integration, and Nguyen Van Phuong et al. (2024) on policies for developing cooperative models in Vietnam. Nevertheless, to date, there has been no study that establishes a comprehensive and appropriate theoretical framework for state support of cooperative development. Moreover, there remains a lack of in-depth research addressing critical questions such as whether cooperative development support policies in Nghe An province over recent years have followed an appropriate direction, whether they have adopted suitable approaches and solutions, and how these policies should be reformed to promote cooperative development and enhance the valuable contributions of the cooperative sector to socio-economic development.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Approach and Analytical Framework

Research approach

This study adopts an approach to cooperative development support policies that emphasizes the creation of an enabling environment for the establishment, operation, and enhancement of the sustainable development of cooperatives. Accordingly, policies supporting cooperative development are categorized into three groups: (1) policies supporting establishment and organizational model transformation; (2) policies supporting production and business operations; and (3) policies supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives. The overarching policy objective is to ensure that cooperatives effectively fulfill their economic, social, and environmental roles. On this basis, the study focuses on the content of provincial government policies supporting cooperative development, including policy foundations, objectives, principles, policy actors, target groups, and the three core policy components—namely, policies supporting establishment and organizational transformation; policies supporting production and business processes; and policies supporting sustainable development. The study does not examine policy formulation or implementation processes.

Analytical framework

The study does not analyze central-level policies; rather, it focuses on provincial-level policies formulated on the basis of central government policy guidelines. By examining provincial policies, the research aims to identify the distinctive features of cooperative support policies in Nghe An province in comparison with central-level support policies. At the same time, this analysis seeks to demonstrate the necessity for the Nghe An provincial government to innovate and reform its cooperative support policies with a degree of relative autonomy, rather than relying excessively on support policies issued by the central government.

The analytical framework of the study is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1.1. Theoretical Framework of Policies Supporting Cooperative Development

Source: Developed by the author

The classification of policy components is based on the stages and objectives of cooperative development at each phase.

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

The first group of policies aims to support cooperatives in entering the market, facilitating the transformation of cooperatives into cooperative unions or enterprise-based models, or enabling cooperatives to re-enter the market more easily after periods of temporary suspension of operations.

The second group of policies targets operating cooperatives, with the objective of promoting production and business activities, attracting labor—particularly rural labor who are cooperative members—and advancing social and community development goals. In the absence of this second group of policies, cooperatives may be established rapidly but are also likely to fail and exit the market just as quickly.

The third group of policies focuses on fostering cooperatives that achieve not only economic objectives but also environmental and social objectives in a sustainable manner. In some countries, these are referred to as policies supporting the development of “new-generation” cooperatives.

2.2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.2.1. Methodological Approach

The methodological approach integrates theories of public policy, cooperative theory, and cooperative development to construct a policy framework for provincial government support of cooperative development. The analysis focuses on the content of cooperative support policies across three groups: policies supporting establishment and organizational model transformation; policies supporting production and business operations; and policies supporting sustainable development. On this basis, a theoretical framework for provincial cooperative development support policies is developed according to three stages: initial market entry of cooperatives; subsequent participation in production and business activities; and finally, the consolidation of production and business outcomes to achieve sustainable development in terms of scale, structure, operational performance, and community development outcomes.

2.2.2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework Development

This study applies theoretical research methods combined with empirical observation, including the summarization and systematization of previous studies according to themes and perspectives using a descriptive approach suitable for research with a broad scope. In addition, a systematic approach is employed throughout the processes of searching for, screening, and organizing relevant studies by theme, followed by systematic analysis, synthesis, and modeling. Integrative analysis combined with critical commentary is used to identify appropriate analytical approaches, develop a new theoretical framework, and identify gaps in the existing literature.

2.2.3. Data Collection Methods

2.2.3.1. Secondary Data Sources

Secondary data were collected using desk research methods, including: domestic and international studies related to cooperatives; statistical data on cooperatives from the General Statistics Office; White Papers on cooperatives published by the Ministry of Planning and Investment for the period 2018–2024; data from programs, plans, and reports of relevant provincial-level state management agencies in Nghe An; documents issued by the Nghe An provincial government; and legal documents and policy materials from the National Assembly, the Government, and relevant ministries concerning policies supporting cooperative development.

2.2.3.2. Primary Data Sources

Primary data were collected through interviews and survey questionnaires.

a) Interviews

Interview subjects: Policy makers, policy implementers, and policy advisors at the provincial level in Nghe An. Seven experts were interviewed from the following institutions: the Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, the Department of Industry and Trade, the Department of Planning and Investment, the Department of Finance, the Department of Natural Resources and Environment, the Department of Home Affairs, and the Nghe An Cooperative Alliance.

Interview objectives: To supplement information for analyzing the current state of cooperative development support policies in Nghe An province.

Interview methods: Individual in-depth interviews and group interviews with officials and experts.

Interview period: October–December 2023.

b) Survey

Survey subjects: Cooperatives operating across different sectors in Nghe An province that are directly affected by cooperative development support policies.

Survey objectives: To provide data for analyzing factors influencing the operational performance of cooperatives in Nghe An province.

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

Survey content: Respondents' assessments of five factors affecting cooperative development outcomes in Nghe An province, including structural capital, social and relational capital, human capital, member participation, and policy support factors.

Data collection method: Structured questionnaires administered through face-to-face interviews or distributed via email and online platforms. After collection, data were checked, cleaned, and coded. A total of 394 valid questionnaires were obtained, meeting the requirements for inclusion in quantitative analysis.

2.2.4. Data Analysis Methods

Both qualitative and quantitative analytical methods were employed, including descriptive statistics, data presentation and interpretation; comparative analysis and evaluation over time; cross-sectional comparative analysis; analysis using representative indicators; case analysis; system analysis; modeling techniques; reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha; exploratory factor analysis; regression analysis; and integrated evaluation methods.

	Criteria	Units of Measurement	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Share of contribution to GRDP							
	Target	%	6,8	6,98	7,16	7,34	7,61	7,92
	Actual Performance	%	6,8	7,5	7,6	7,4	7,5	7,7
	Assessment		Achieved	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Not achieved	Not achieved
2	Total number of cooperatives							
	Target	CO-OP	686	745	788	816	852	910
	Actual Performance	CO-OP	699	740	780	822	862	902
	Assessment		Exceeded	Not achieved	Not achieved	Exceeded	Exceeded	Not achieved
3	Total number of cooperative members							
	Target	People	243.921	244.485	244.961	245.481	246.003	246.524
	Actual Performance	People	266.921	266.975	267.125	267.850	267.976	268.186
	Assessment		Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded
4	Number of permanent employees in cooperatives							
	Target	People	59.310	59.813	60.321	60.845	61.401	61.956
	Actual Performance	People	59.310	59.813	60.321	60.845	60.976	61.126
	Assessment		Achieved	Achieved	Achieved	Achieved	Not achieved	Not achieved
5	Total operating capital of cooperatives							
	Target	Million VND	4.763.210	5.121.725	5.231.000	5.232.121	5.234.121	5.244.238
	Actual Performance	Million VND	4.332.106	5.121.725	5.231.000	5.200.000	5.625.000	6.138.000
	Assessment		Not achieved	Achieved	Achieved	Achieved	Exceeded	Exceeded
6	Total asset value of cooperatives							
	Target	Million VND	3.150.000	3.450.000	3.900.000	3.975.000	4.012.500	4.387.500

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

	Actual Performance	Million VND	3.563.968	3.600.755	3.735.654	3.800.000	4.209.000	4.560.000
	Assessment		Exceeded	Exceeded	Not achieved	Not achieved	Exceeded	Exceeded
7	Average annual revenue per cooperative							
	Target	Million VND	1900	1950	2050	2.160	2.300	2.300
	Actual Performance	Million VND	1933	2032	2136	2.203	2.373	2.542
	Assessment		Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded
8	Average annual profit per cooperative							
	Target	Million VND	150	160	170	180	190	200
	Actual Performance	Million VND	141	151	162	171	175	190
	Assessment		Not achieved					
9	Average annual income of permanent employees in cooperatives							
	Target	Million VND	51	53	54	56	70	72
	Actual Performance	Million VND	52,8	53,7	54,9	56	54,7	58
	Assessment		Exceeded	Exceeded	Exceeded	Achieved	Not achieved	Not achieved

Source: Calculated from data of the Nghe An Provincial People's Committee (2021c, 2024).

The results regarding the contribution of cooperatives to GRDP indicate that during the period 2018–2021, the targets for cooperative contributions were achieved; however, from 2022 onward, this contribution declined relative to expectations.

An assessment based on the number of cooperatives shows that Nghe An province experienced a relatively rapid increase in the number of cooperatives, although the targets set for the years 2019, 2020, and 2023 were not fully met.

An evaluation of cooperative membership participation indicates that targets for member development were achieved in all years during the 2018–2024 period. This suggests that cooperatives in Nghe An province possess considerable attractiveness and make significant contributions from a social perspective. Nevertheless, average annual income per worker remains low and has not met the established targets.

With regard to the number of regular workers participating in cooperatives, the targets were achieved during the 2018–2021 period; however, outcomes for 2022 and 2023 fell short of the stated objectives.

An assessment based on financial indicators reveals that, while average revenue targets were generally met, profit per cooperative failed to reach the policy targets. At the same time, asset and capital indicators remain unstable and vulnerable.

Despite the notable achievements in cooperative development within the province, several policy objectives have not yet been fulfilled, particularly those related to the quality of cooperative operations, which remain concentrated primarily in the agricultural cooperative sector. In Nghe An, although the proportion of effectively operating agricultural cooperatives is higher than the national average, they account for only 59% of the total number of cooperatives in the province. Moreover, to date, only approximately one-third of agricultural cooperatives have established production linkages associated with agricultural product consumption. A key challenge is that most agricultural cooperatives operate with very limited capital, and access to bank credit under existing credit policies is extremely difficult due to the lack of collateral. As a result, these cooperatives lack the financial capacity to invest in high-value machinery, as well as in factories, wharves, warehouses, and facilities for preliminary processing and processing, thereby constraining the expansion of production linkages. Box 3.9 in Appendix 6 illustrates the situation of stagnating operations among several cooperatives in Nghe An province.

3.2. Strengths of the Policy Framework

Overall, Nghe An province has formulated and implemented cooperative development support policies in addition to those issued at the central level. These policies have contributed to an increase in the number of newly established cooperatives, the expansion

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

of cooperative operations, and a gradual shift toward more sustainable development in terms of production and business performance, environmental protection, and food safety. Policy principles are clearly articulated in each specific policy document, while policy purposes and objectives define both general targets and specific indicators for supporting cooperative development in the province across different stages of cooperative development.

Policies supporting establishment and organizational model transformation

In recent years, Nghe An province has made considerable efforts to promulgate policies supporting the establishment of new cooperatives, particularly in the agricultural sector. The province has introduced a number of regulations classified as policies supporting cooperative formation, such as support measures for newly established cooperatives and exemptions from business registration fees. In addition, policies supporting organizational model transformation have been implemented, including measures to encourage cooperatives to develop following enterprise-oriented models.

Policies supporting production and business operations of cooperatives

Nghe An has also proactively issued a coherent set of policies to support cooperative production and business activities in alignment with central government orientations. Several provincial support policies fall within this category, including policies facilitating access to capital; land-use support policies; policies supporting infrastructure development; policies on human resource training and capacity building; and policies providing technical assistance, market information access, and trade promotion. These policies reflect the strong commitment of the provincial government to reducing constraints, creating opportunities, and establishing favorable conditions for sustaining cooperative operations and promoting their development.

Policies supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives

The Nghe An provincial government has demonstrated increased attention to supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives through more robust and innovative policy initiatives compared to earlier periods. The province has introduced policies to promote digitalization and the application of electronic technologies in cooperatives, as well as policies supporting cooperative linkages with stakeholders along supply chains—often referred to as policies for developing “new-generation” cooperatives. These include support for consultancy costs in building linkages; infrastructure support for cooperative linkages; support for training and capacity building; provision of inputs such as seeds, materials, packaging, and product labeling; support for the “One Commune One Product” (OCOP) program; support for processing, preservation, and marketing of agricultural, forestry, and aquatic products while ensuring food safety; support for technology transfer and the application of new scientific and technical advances; support for production inputs including raw materials, plant and animal varieties, fertilizers, animal feed, plant protection chemicals, veterinary drugs, tools, equipment, and machinery for production and service provision; support for project and plan formulation and management; support for the adoption of advanced standards, tools, models, and management methods; support for the development and application of product and commodity standards; support for the implementation of traceability systems; and support for participation in trade fairs and exhibitions to promote products within supply chains.

3.3. Limitations of the Policies and Their Underlying Causes

a) Policy limitations

Policies supporting the establishment of new cooperatives and organizational model transformation

The content of existing policies remains limited in scope, as reflected in the narrow range of provisions supporting the establishment of new cooperatives. Support for new cooperative formation is largely confined to agricultural cooperatives, despite the increasing importance of non-agricultural cooperatives in the context of rural development. In addition, most cooperative founders lack sufficient knowledge and a comprehensive understanding of cooperative principles, member mobilization methods, and the preparation of initial business plans. Meanwhile, initial operational support policies have not yet been issued, and establishment support is only disbursed after cooperatives are formally established.

Beyond financial support, the province lacks regulations on non-financial support measures such as information provision, consultancy, training, and dissemination of legal regulations related to the collective economy and cooperatives. There is also insufficient support for consultancy services related to drafting cooperative charters, developing production and business plans, and organizing members' congresses in accordance with current legal requirements.

Another significant limitation is that existing support policies do not include specific incentives encouraging cooperatives to transform into enterprise-oriented models, despite the stated policy objective of promoting such transformations. Policies supporting cooperatives' re-entry into the market after periods of temporary suspension have received limited attention. Moreover, Nghe An has yet to establish mechanisms to encourage cooperatives to participate in cooperative unions.

Policies supporting production and business operations

Support policies governing cooperative operations impose access conditions that remain relatively restrictive, particularly with respect to land and capital support. Capital support policies involve complex lending procedures, while cooperatives often lack the capacity to develop feasible, low-risk business plans required to access bank credit. Land access support policies are insufficiently

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

robust beyond rent subsidies, and procedures for receiving land rent support remain cumbersome. Provincial land allocation regulations lack practical feasibility, as land is largely allocated to households; consequently, organizations seeking land for facilities must compensate land users subject to land acquisition. This situation stems from the absence of land-use planning policies specifically designed to support cooperative development.

Several support policies provide limited content or low levels of assistance that are insufficient to address cooperatives' challenges, such as policies on human resource training and capacity building and policies supporting infrastructure investment. Nghe An's policies are also constrained by central government regulations, such as restrictions on the use of central budget funds for Group C infrastructure investment projects supporting cooperatives. In addition, some policies define target groups inappropriately or too narrowly. For example, human resource support policies aimed at enhancing capacity and awareness within cooperatives fail to prioritize workers directly engaged in production and business activities. Similarly, provisions on training subsidies differentiate between agricultural and non-agricultural cooperatives, resulting in inequitable treatment across cooperative types. Overall support levels remain modest and have limited impact.

Furthermore, the province has not introduced measures to support technical skill development for cooperative member-workers or to enhance legal and managerial capacities of cooperative leaders. Several important support policies are absent, including policies to develop networks of consultancy service providers, technology and technical transfer services, financial analysis support, and access to market information (legal and economic information, market surveys and research, forecasting, and early warning of trade defense measures for export products). Some policy solutions are based on support criteria that are poorly aligned with the actual conditions of cooperatives, while other policies are overly detailed, fragmented, and difficult to implement.

Policies supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives

Policies supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives remain at an early and preliminary stage. In practice, central-level policies in this area are still limited and have not yet created a sufficiently enabling legal environment to guide and facilitate provincial policy initiatives. Policies promoting digital transformation and the application of e-commerce in cooperatives tend to be short-term, with fragmented and unfocused support measures that lack the capacity to generate long-term spillover effects.

Nghe An province has yet to introduce comprehensive support regulations to assist cooperatives in environmental protection, and existing provisions on food safety support are insufficient to create sustained incentives for cooperatives. Policies supporting agricultural production linkages along supply chains, or the development of "new-generation" cooperatives, remain partial and lack a comprehensive and coherent approach. These policies are not sufficiently robust to motivate cooperatives to pursue supply chain-based development, as they are fragmented and lack integration across inputs, production processes, outputs, and supply chain design and management.

Moreover, support for supply chain development has not been adequately aligned with economic, social, and environmental objectives of supply chain development projects. Beyond existing policies supporting supply chain linkages in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, Nghe An province has not yet promulgated policies to support cooperative participation in supply chains in industrial and handicraft sectors.

b) Causes of the Policy Limitations

Causes related to policy formulation

In recent years, shortcomings in the policy formulation process of the Nghe An provincial government have resulted in cooperative development support policies that lack practical relevance, thereby affecting the achievement of policy objectives—particularly with regard to operational efficiency and the sustainable development of cooperatives. The main limitations include insufficient coordination in the proposal and issuance of policies, as well as a lack of empirical evidence on the actual development status and needs of cooperatives during policy design. In addition, budgetary resource constraints have been a key factor shaping policy priorities and orientations.

Causes related to policy implementation

At the implementation stage, dissemination activities and the development of specific programs and action plans for policy execution have not adequately ensured practical applicability or timely support for cooperatives. Moreover, cooperative development involves multiple sectoral departments, making the allocation of functions and responsibilities relatively complex due to the diversity of cooperative types and the interdisciplinary nature of many tasks. While provincial departments have made efforts to allocate resources to strengthen and improve the production and business performance of cooperatives, establish new-generation cooperatives linked to value chains, and conduct training and capacity-building activities, available resources remain limited. Budget allocations are dispersed across multiple objectives, resulting in insufficient funding to effectively implement cooperative development support policies.

The management of cooperative activities is closely linked to district-level governments, yet the policy implementation capacity of district authorities in Nghe An province remains limited. This constitutes a significant barrier to the effective implementation of cooperative development support policies. In addition, advisory and consultancy services provided to cooperatives are ineffective

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

and lack adequate quality. As a result, cooperatives in the province face constraints in transforming their operational models, developing production and business activities based on new-generation cooperative models linked to value chain development, and expanding the number of products meeting OCOP standards.

Causes related to the micro-level environment

Cooperative members' financial capacity to contribute capital remains limited. Market experience within cooperatives is constrained by insufficient awareness of market mechanisms, and members' knowledge and experience related to market dynamics remain underdeveloped. Small-scale production mindsets continue to dominate, posing barriers to innovation in production and business activities. Furthermore, cooperatives in Nghe An province have not sufficiently developed social capital and lack strong linkages with socio-political organizations, social organizations, professional associations, and other influential actors that could provide support for their development. Meanwhile, provincial cooperative support policies have not adequately accounted for these micro-level factors, resulting in policies that lack practical relevance and, in some cases, are misaligned with cooperative characteristics—particularly policies related to access to capital, access to land, and sustainable development support.

Causes related to the macro-level environment

The Nghe An Provincial Cooperative Alliance has not effectively coordinated the review and assessment of cooperative activities, cooperative unions, and previously invested or established models, nor has it effectively advised the Provincial People's Committee on cooperative development support policies. At the national level, relevant ministries and agencies have not yet issued comprehensive guiding circulars for the 2023 Law on Cooperatives and Decree No. 113/2024/NĐ-CP. The legal framework serving as the basis for provincial cooperative support policies remains incomplete, particularly with respect to frameworks for supporting the sustainable development of cooperatives across economic, social, and environmental pillars.

In addition, ministries and sectoral agencies have not promptly advised on the completion of sector- and field-specific cooperative development support policies, leaving local governments without sufficient legal benchmarks for comparison, alignment, and avoidance of policy overlap between provincial and central levels. The information system on cooperatives lacks coherence and consistency, and criteria and indicators for monitoring and evaluating cooperative development remain unclear. Existing data on cooperative development also lack systematic reporting on social and environmental outcomes.

3.4. Assessment of the Impact of Factors affecting the Outcomes of Cooperatives Development in Nghe An Province

The objective of this section is to test the hypothesis: "Policies supporting cooperative development have a positive impact on cooperative development outcomes." This allows for an assessment of whether the cooperative support policies implemented in Nghe An Province in recent years are genuinely important and the extent to which they play a significant role in the development of cooperatives operating in the province.

If the hypothesis is supported, it implies that the cooperative development support policies in Nghe An Province are indeed important and make a substantial contribution to cooperative development outcomes, thereby justifying the continuation of such policies. Conversely, if the hypothesis is not supported, it would suggest that these policies should be discontinued in order to avoid inefficient use of public resources.

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

Figure 2. Research Model of Factors Affecting Cooperative Development Outcomes

Source: Adapted from Khan et al. (2016) and Efendiev and Sorokin (2013)

At the end of the survey process, a total of 394 valid questionnaires were collected. Detailed characteristics of the research sample are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the Survey Sample

Sample description	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Cooperative size		
Large-scale	62	15,7
Medium-scale	98	24,9
Small-scale	234	59,4
Sector of operation		
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	256	65,0
Trade and services	121	30,7
Industry and construction	17	4,3
Years of operation		
Under 3 years	49	12,4
3-5 years	40	10,2
5-10 years	138	35,0
More than 10 years	167	42,4

Source: Authors' analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis of the variables, including mean values, standard deviations, minimum and maximum values, indicates that the dataset consists of 394 complete observations with no missing data. The mean values range from 3.39 to 3.77, suggesting that respondents generally tended to agree with the given statements. Standard deviations below 1 indicate a high level

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

of response concentration. Overall, the survey results reveal positive perceptions across most dimensions, with development outcomes (KQ) emerging as a key strength, while human resources (NL) represent an area requiring further improvement. Variations in standard deviations also provide useful insights into the degree of consensus or diversity in evaluations across different dimensions.

The reliability of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha in order to eliminate inappropriate observed variables. The analysis was conducted on six composite variables in the research model, including one dependent variable and five independent variables. The results show that Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for all factor groups exceed the threshold of 0.7, indicating that the observed variables within each group consistently measure the same underlying construct. Overall, the measurement scales demonstrate good reliability and are suitable for further analysis, while also providing meaningful insights into the role of each factor in the model.

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha Results for Measurement Scales

No.	Factor	Measurements Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	CT	CT1, CT2, CT3, CT4	0,767
2	QH	QH1, QH2, QH3	0,821
3	NL	NL1, NL2, NL3, NL4, NL5, NL6, NL7	0,847
4	TG	TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7	0,84
5	CS	CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS5	0,84
6	KQ	KQ1, KQ2, KQ3, KQ4, KQ5, KQ6, KQ7	0,849

Source: Authors' analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted on the observed variables in the model. The results of the KMO and Bartlett's tests are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.901
Approx. Chi-Square	894.763
Df	21
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Sig. .000

Source: Authors' analysis

The KMO value of 0.901 exceeds the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.5, and the significance level of Bartlett's test (Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05) indicates that the null hypothesis of no correlation among observed variables is rejected. This confirms that the observed variables are sufficiently correlated and suitable for factor analysis. The cumulative explained variance reaches 52.554%, exceeding the 50% threshold, indicating that the five extracted factors explain 52.554% of the total variance in the data.

Regression Analysis Results

The standardized regression equation is as follows:

$$QD = 0.174*CT + 0.239*QH + 0.197*NL + 0.292*TG + 0.266*CS + \epsilon$$

Table 5. Estimation Results of the Research Model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.031	.140		-.223	.823
	CT	.164	.032	.174	5.124	.000

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

QH	.211	.030	.239	6.992	.000
NL	.193	.033	.197	5.881	.000
TG	.290	.034	.292	8.660	.000
CS	.236	.030	.266	7.858	.000

Source: Authors' analysis

The results indicate that:

- Structural capital has a positive effect on cooperative development outcomes ($\beta = 0.164$, $p < 0.001$); therefore, Hypothesis H1 is supported.
- Relational capital has a positive effect on cooperative development outcomes ($\beta = 0.211$, $p < 0.001$); therefore, Hypothesis H2 is supported.
- Human capital has a positive effect on cooperative development outcomes ($\beta = 0.193$, $p < 0.001$); therefore, Hypothesis H3 is supported.
- Member participation has a positive effect on cooperative development outcomes ($\beta = 0.290$, $p < 0.001$); therefore, Hypothesis H4 is supported.
- Support policies for cooperative development have a positive effect on cooperative development outcomes ($\beta = 0.236$, $p < 0.001$); therefore, Hypothesis H5 is supported.

The findings demonstrate that policies supporting cooperative development are a key factor influencing cooperative development outcomes in Nghe An Province in recent years. This confirms the critical role of provincial authorities in designing and implementing cooperative support policies. Consequently, the continuation of cooperative development support policies is both necessary and justified.

4. Policy Recommendations for Improving Cooperative Development Support Policies in Nghe An Province

4.1. Policies Supporting Cooperative Establishment and Organizational Transformation

a. Policies Supporting Cooperative Establishment

In order to achieve the target of establishing 40–45 new cooperatives annually, including approximately 35 agricultural cooperatives, and to eliminate “cooperative-free” communes, Nghe An Province should continue to maintain policies supporting the establishment of new cooperatives. The minimum support level in the coming period should be set at VND 50 million per cooperative, which is comparable to support levels in other provinces.

According to feedback from cooperatives and state management officials, the current support level of VND 20–30 million per cooperative is relatively low compared to support levels nationwide and provides limited incentives for the establishment of new cooperatives. Moreover, fragmented and widely dispersed support tends to be ineffective.

Regulations on financial support for newly established cooperatives should be accompanied by clear provisions on initial support contents, including the provision of information, consultancy, training, and dissemination of legal regulations on the collective economy and cooperatives; support and consultancy in developing cooperative charters; assistance in formulating business plans; and support for organizing members' congresses of collective economic organizations and cooperatives. These measures would address the lack of knowledge and limited understanding among founding members regarding cooperative principles, member mobilization, and the formulation of initial business plans.

In addition to policies supporting the establishment of new cooperatives, fee exemption policies should be expanded to cover a wider range of beneficiaries, not limited to policy-priority groups but applicable to any individuals or organizations wishing to establish cooperatives. The scope of support should include initial registration fees, fees for issuing new cooperative registration certificates, and fees for reissuing or amending registration certificates.

Implementation measures may include the development of a provincial-level program specifying initial support levels and flexible disbursement mechanisms, with the Provincial Cooperative Alliance or the Provincial Cooperative Development Fund designated as the focal agency for appraisal and disbursement.

b. Policies Supporting Organizational Transformation

Policies should be developed to support cooperatives in transforming into enterprises and in forming cooperative unions through linkages. The minimum support level may be referenced from other localities, such as Vinh Phuc Province, where support ranges from VND 80–100 million per successfully transformed case.

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

Funding sources may include provincial budget allocations for economic development, integration with resources from the National Target Program on New Rural Development, the Sustainable Poverty Reduction Program, or the Socio-economic Development Program for Ethnic Minority and Mountainous Areas.

Specific implementation measures should include clear assignment of responsibilities regarding funding allocation, appraisal, and outcome monitoring, as well as the establishment of transparent and publicly disclosed procedures on the Nghe An Provincial Government's official portal.

4.2. Improving Policies Supporting Production and Business Activities

a. Policies Supporting Access to Finance

Nghe An Province should consider developing a dedicated credit policy for cooperatives. Beyond interest rate subsidies, greater emphasis should be placed on simplifying procedures and credit conditions tailored to the operational characteristics of cooperatives. Flexible debt repayment mechanisms suitable for different types of cooperatives should also be explored.

Provincial authorities should strengthen coordination among the Cooperative Development Fund, the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, and the Vietnam Bank for Social Policies to simplify lending conditions for cooperatives. This approach addresses the practical challenges cooperatives face in accessing credit, including small scale, weak competitiveness, loose organizational structures, limited managerial capacity, lack of collateral, constrained capital mobilization, and business plans with limited feasibility. Additionally, agricultural cooperatives are exposed to high risks from natural disasters and crop failures, which further discourages commercial banks from extending credit.

Following the Government's guidance on implementing the 2023 Cooperative Law regarding the integration of credit resources from National Target Programs, Nghe An Province should issue policies prioritizing and allocating integrated funding from the National Target Program on New Rural Development and the National Target Program on Socio-economic Development of Ethnic Minority and Mountainous Areas to facilitate cooperative access to finance.

The role of the Cooperative Development Fund should be strengthened through linkages with credit institutions, preferential interest rates and fees, support in preparing feasible loan proposals, diversification of linked funding sources, and the establishment of transparent and equitable monitoring mechanisms.

b. Policies Supporting Land Access

Short-term measures may include regulations allowing cooperatives to use land within the premises of commune-level People's Committees, or to borrow office space or members' houses for use as temporary offices or headquarters.

At the provincial level, Nghe An authorities should develop land-use planning orientations that allocate land specifically for cooperatives. This constitutes an essential foundation enabling cooperatives to secure land for their operations. Additionally, preferential policies for land-use purpose conversion should be considered to facilitate cooperatives' production and business activities.

In the long term, the provincial government and the Nghe An Cooperative Alliance should propose policies on land allocation and land leasing for cooperatives, as well as collective land ownership arrangements among cooperative members. These policies fall under the jurisdiction of central authorities and would require amendments to the Land Law and Civil Code to facilitate cooperative access to land resources.

c. Policies Supporting Human Resource Training and Capacity Building

Nghe An Province should develop a comprehensive policy framework for supporting training and capacity building for cooperative human resources. Beneficiaries should include all cooperatives operating within the province, with the objective of equipping cooperative personnel with management skills, business law knowledge, sector-specific expertise, and competencies in financial and human resource management.

The provincial government should clearly define the scope of supported training activities. Priority areas that are currently lacking among cooperatives include digital transformation and the application of information technology in trade promotion; long-term cooperative governance training for boards of directors and management teams; technical training by sector; training on the adoption of new technologies; business planning and production organization; marketing management; service management within cooperatives; cooperative development linked to value chains; financial statement analysis; cooperative accounting; accounting software utilization; internal control; and internal auditing.

d. Policies Supporting Investment in Infrastructure and Equipment

Existing provincial support policies should be reviewed and revised to focus on investment in infrastructure and equipment for newly established cooperatives, cooperatives in planned craft villages, and cooperatives operating in planned industrial clusters and zones. Priority should be given to cooperatives in key agricultural sectors and those meeting OCOP standards. Current fragmented support mechanisms are inefficient, wasteful, and insufficient to incentivize the establishment and development of cooperatives in strategic areas.

Conditions for receiving support for infrastructure and equipment investment should be simplified to ensure cooperatives can meet

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

eligibility requirements, such as compliance with environmental safety standards, proof of planning costs, and verification that supported equipment is newly purchased and aligned with approved production or investment plans.

Policies on support modalities should be revised to combine post-investment and pre-/during-investment support mechanisms. This approach would help alleviate financial constraints and enhance cooperatives' willingness to engage with government support programs.

e. Policies Supporting Technical Expertise, Market Information Access, and Trade Promotion

Nghe An Province should develop policies supporting technical expertise and access to market information for cooperatives. This represents a critical policy component currently missing from the cooperative support system and has a significant impact on cooperative performance.

Technical support policies may include the development of consultancy and technology transfer networks for cooperatives, as well as advisory services covering cooperative accounting, financial management, and the dissemination of best practices from exemplary cooperatives. Technology transfer may be facilitated through pilot models implemented at the local level.

Market information support policies may include legal and economic information services, market surveys and research, and forecasting and early warning mechanisms related to trade remedies. The province should also support cooperatives in conducting market surveys and research activities.

4.3. Improving Policies for Sustainable Cooperative Development

a. General Recommendations for Digital Transformation, Innovation, and Value Chain Linkage Policies

The beneficiaries of policies supporting digital transformation, innovation, and cooperative linkages within supply chains should be cooperatives implementing specific projects in these areas. These policies should apply to cooperatives across all economic sectors, not only agricultural cooperatives, as agricultural cooperatives can only effectively participate in supply chains with the involvement of non-agricultural cooperatives, enterprises, and other stakeholders.

Support resources should be designed as integrated project-based packages rather than fragmented support for isolated activities. Moreover, these policies should incorporate monitoring and evaluation components based on outcome-oriented criteria. Decisions on the continuation or termination of support should depend on cooperatives' economic, social, and environmental performance.

Effective implementation measures include the development of a cooperative information portal, public disclosure of procedures, criteria, and beneficiary lists, and the promotion of digital governance and traceability systems within cooperatives.

b. Specific Recommendations for Digital Transformation and Innovation Support Policies

The provincial government should develop policies supporting science and technology innovation projects within cooperatives, including projects involving the adoption and transfer of new production technologies, as well as the protection and development of cooperative intellectual property assets. Priority should be given to projects involving green technologies, encouraging cooperatives to adopt environmentally sustainable innovations.

In addition to supporting product and service innovation, these policies should be integrated with internal digital transformation initiatives to enhance overall cooperative management efficiency.

c. Specific Recommendations for Cooperative Value Chain Linkage Policies

Policies supporting cooperative linkages within supply chains should adopt a comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges faced by cooperatives. Supported projects should cover access to finance, infrastructure development, human resource training, input costs (such as seeds, materials, packaging, and labeling), output quality enhancement, processing and preservation, food safety assurance, trade promotion, linkage design, and the application of advanced standards, tools, and management models.

Comprehensive, project-based support for value chain linkages would help overcome the inefficiencies associated with fragmented policy implementation currently observed in Nghe An Province.

5. CONCLUSION

Cooperative development support policies implemented by the Nghe An provincial government play a pivotal role in shaping development orientations, creating a favorable operating environment, and removing barriers for the cooperative sector. These policies serve as an essential instrument for translating central government directives into local practice, thereby promoting sustainable cooperative development.

Improving these policies is necessary to address existing shortcomings, including limited coordination, insufficient alignment with cooperative needs, and delays in policy implementation. Well-designed, feasible, and effective policies will provide strong incentives for cooperative development, contributing to the province's socio-economic growth. Therefore, refining cooperative development support policies in Nghe An Province is an urgent requirement to fully realize the role of cooperatives in both economic activities and community development.

Provincial Government Policies Supporting Cooperative Development: A Case Study in Vietnam

REFERENCES

- 1) Adeler, M.C., (2014). Enabling policy environments for cooperative development: A comparative experience. Canadian Public Policy/Analyse de Politiques Vol. 40, Supplement I.
- 2) Ministry of Planning and Investment (2023a), Vietnam Cooperative White Paper 2023. Statistical Publishing House.
- 3) Ministry of Planning and Investment (2023b). Voluntary National Review Report 2023. Accessed at [https://fileportalcms.mpi.gov.vn/TinBai/VanBan/2023-08/VNR_Full_Final\(EN\).pdf](https://fileportalcms.mpi.gov.vn/TinBai/VanBan/2023-08/VNR_Full_Final(EN).pdf).
- 4) Ministry of Planning and Investment (2024, Vietnam Cooperative White Paper 2024. Statistical Publishing House).
- 5) Nghe An Provincial People's Council (2021a). Resolution 18/2021/NQ-HĐND dated December 9, 2021, promulgating regulations on some policies to support the development of agriculture and rural areas in Nghe An province for the period 2021-2025.
- 6) Nghe An Provincial People's Council (2021b). Resolution No. 22/2021/NQ-HĐND stipulating a number of policies for the development of industry and small-scale handicrafts in Nghe An province.
- 7) Nghe An Provincial People's Council (2022b). Resolution No. 07/2022/NQ-HĐND stipulating business registration fees in Nghe An province.
- 8) Rowe, J. K., Peredo, A. M., Sullivan, M., & Restakis, J. (2018). Policy supports for co-operative development: Learning from co-op hot spots. *Journal of Co-operative Studies*, 51(1), p 39–42.
- 9) Nguyen Van Phuong, Truong Anh Tuan, Dinh Thi Thanh Tam, & Ly Thu Cuc (2024). Research on policy development of cooperative models in Vietnam. *Finance Magazine*. <https://tapchitaichinh.vn/nghien-cuu-chinh-sach-phan-trien-mo-hinh-hop-tac-xa-tai-viet-nam.html>
- 10) Khan, H. A., Yaacob, M. A., Abdullah, H., & Abu Bakar Ah, S. H. (2016). Factors affecting performance of co-operatives in Malaysia. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 65(5), p 641–671. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-02-2015-0028>.
- 11) Efendiev, A., and Pavel Sorokin (2013). Rural social organization and farmer cooperatives development in Russia and other emerging economies: comparative analysis. *Developing Country Studies* 3.14 (2013): p 106-115.
- 12) ILO (2014). The role of cooperatives in achieving the sustainable development goals - the economic dimension. A Contribution to the UN DESA Expert Group Meeting and Workshop on Cooperatives.
- 13) Nguyễn Thị Hải Ninh (2021), Policies supporting for agricultural cooperatives in Vietnam: An experience from agricultural cooperatives in the Red River Delta". *Technium Social Sciences Journal* Vol. 25, November, 2021 ISSN: 2668-7798 www.techniumscience.com.
- 14) OECD & FAO. (2016). OECD–FAO guidance for responsible agricultural supply chains. OECD Publishing & FAO. <https://mneguidelines.oecd.org/OECD-FAO-Guidance.pdf>
- 15) OECD (2020). The Role of Cooperatives in the New Global Economy. Paris: OECD Publishing. Accessed at <https://www.oecd.org/industry/role-of-cooperatives.htm>.
- 16) Nguyen Thi Hai Yen (2018). Developing Nghe An's agriculture towards modernization in the context of international economic integration. Doctoral dissertation in Economics, Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences.
- 17) People's Committee of Nghe An Province (2021a). Decision No. 1958/QĐ-UBND dated June 18, 2021 approving the "Project to continue innovation and development of cooperatives in Nghe An province giai đoạn 2021-2025".
- 18) People's Committee of Nghe An Province (2021b). Plan No. 195/KH UBND: Implementation of the Strategy for the Development of Collective Economy and Cooperatives giai đoạn 2021–2030 according to Decision No. 340/QĐ TTg dated March 12, 2021.
- 19) People's Committee of Nghe An Province (2021c). Report on the Strategic Orientation for the Development of Collective Economy and Cooperatives in Nghe An Province, 2021-2030.
- 20) People's Committee of Nghe An province (2024), Report on the current status and development plan of cooperative unions, cooperatives, and cooperative groups in 2022-2024.